

Examining the Implementation and Oversight of Food Serving Robots in Restaurant Operations: Insights from Operators in Bangalore

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Abstract - The integration of robot technology has a paradigm shift, particularly in the domain of food service within hotels of Bangalore. This abstract explores the implementation of autonomous food serving robots, and also their impact on enhancing guest experience, operational efficiency, management and overall customer satisfaction in Bangalore. The primary objectives of food serving robots include streamlining operations, reducing human error etc. In view from Bangalore through a comprehensive review, this abstract shows how hotels worldwide are leveraging these robots to optimize workflows, increase staff productivity, and elevate the level of service provided to guests.

The abstract discusses the economic considerations with implementing food serving robots, addressing initial investment costs, operational savings, and management services of the robot restaurants from Bangalore. While comparing with the real-world, the abstract provides insights into the tangible benefits experienced by hotels that have this kind of innovative technology. And some of the restaurants come across failure due to this robotic transformation.

In conclusion, the abstract highlights the impact of autonomous food serving robots, emphasizing their role in services and creating memorable guest experiences in Bangalore robotic restaurants. The integration of these robots not only addresses operational challenges and it also

aligns with the expectations of modern travelers looking for a harmonious blend of technology and hospitality

Keywords: Food Serving Robots, hospitality management, staff training, Operational efficiency, examining food serving robots, Robotic innovation, customer trust.

I. INTRODUCTION

In modern days, the integration of robotic technology has emerged in various fields. They are so efficient nowadays. The transformative advancements in the restaurant industry, where the deployment of food serving robots is reshaping the landscape of culinary service [1]. And some hospitality management also provides these types of robotic technology. This research shows the implementation and oversight of food serving robots in restaurant operations, offering valuable insights drawn directly from the experiences and perspectives of operators within the field.

The introduction of robotics in resorts or restaurants represents a significant paradigm shift, introducing automation into a traditionally human-centric domain. These food serving robots show that it has high speed on the consumer expectation [1][2]. However, the successful transformation of these technological innovations necessitates a comprehensive understanding of the challenges, benefits, and operations faced by restaurant operators.

This research aims at the technological innovation and practical implementation of real-world experiences of those operating within the industry. By examining the food serving robots into restaurant operations, this study seeks to identify best practices, potentials, and the overall impact on customer satisfaction and business performance [1][2]. Furthermore, the research explores the regulatory and ethical considerations associated with the deployment of such automation, ensuring a holistic evaluation of the implications for both businesses and the broader societal landscape.

II .OBJECTIVE

The objective of the study is to explore the implementation and impact of food serving robots in hotels. The study aims to analyze the advantages and disadvantages of integrating robotic technology in the hotels and resorts, with a specific focus on food service. And some of the hotels experience some disadvantages with the robotic operation. And these failures also focus on the research areas. The researcher also aims to get insights from operators.

III . ROBOTS IN THE FOOD & BEVERAGE INDUSTRY

The use of robotics in many sectors, such as a robot restaurant, or in a beverage field has been driven by improved AI software as well as the reduction of the cost of hardware, such as sensors and circuit boards. Robots help both business and customers, and they enhance the entire experience. In this emerging world, robots become more prevalent and it affects the food chains all over the world. In some beverage restaurants automated robotic technology is witnessed. The drinks are served to customers to their satisfaction by the robots. In the high cost of resorts also we can see these types of robots doing all the operations. Many of them are not aware of using these robots in the Beverage Industry. Mostly, outside Kerala there seems to be robotic innovation in Beverages.

a) Kerala's First Robotic Hotel Opens in Kannur

Be Kiwizo was initially launched as the first food delivery app in Kannur, the aim is to serve food in a homely nature. After the app became popular among foodies, the team which comprised of Malayalam actor Maniyanpilla Raju, Nizamuddin C.V., Sajma Nizamudhin and Vineeth M.K., put their thought to how innovative technology could be brought into the management sector.

The robots are also programmed to say: 'Your favorite food is ready'. A team is managing the robotic operations. Besides Helen, Aleena and Jane

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who serve food, another robot named Abdu entertains children who come to the restaurant. And the customers were rushing to this restaurant. From distant places they are coming for this delicious food and also want to experience this robotic service [2][3].

Customers order the food through tabs placed on the table. Once an order is received, the worker keeps the food directly in the hands of the robot. The robots identify the ordered table through the radio frequency which is placed near every table.

When the food reaches the diners table they are allowed to touch on the sensor behind it. The dining cost will not be much expensive compared with other restaurants. And though comparatively the robotic maintenance is of high cost. The robots need to be serviced every month.

All those robots are imported from China, each robot costs Rs. 15 lakhs. The waitress robots are 5 feet tall. The robot walks through the magnet fixed on the floor. The robots are pre-programmed ones which work on the basis of sensors kept[3][7].

b) Robotic Experience in Chennai

The Robotic Restaurant in Chennai was Founded by Karthik Kannan, and Venkatesh Rajendran, the restaurant comprises a total of four robot waiters who serve food to the people at their tables. The Robotic Restaurant also portrays Chinese and Thai food.

This robotic restaurant was Located on the famous Old Mahabalipuram Road in Chennai, this is said to be the first robotic restaurant in India. The Robots are the main essence of this restaurant which operates on the sensors placed. When anyone blocks the way, they can identify using these sensors placed on them [3].

c) How to Order Food in This Restaurant?

The **Robotic restaurant Chennai**, takes much pride in its uniqueness of ordering food. With the new technology it is said that while ordering the food through the tabs given the request is sent to the kitchen.

When the food is ready the robot serves the ordered table. And the customers dine in with a new customer experience.

d) *Why Is a Robot Restaurant So Special?*

The restaurant is the first ever Robotic themed café with high technology. There are also two other outlets of this restaurant in Chennai. And there are four bots placed at the entrance for welcoming the customers which are controlled by humans. In order to take the order, there is a tab kept on each specified table. After selecting the menu, the robots will serve the food. This seems good when one wants to avoid human contact [8].

e) *Advantages:*

- Food-serving robots can enhance operational efficiency by reducing wait times, order fulfillment, and the overall dining experience.
- Automation can lead to reduced labor costs as robots can handle time-consuming tasks.
- Robots can provide service without any variability.
- Unlike human employees, robots can work on late nights and early mornings. They can work continuously.
- Food-serving robots minimize the contact with customers and also more hygiene is provided. Because compared to humans they are less in contact.
- The food-serving robots can attract customers seeking a unique dining experience, potentially increasing business and creating competition in the field.
- Robots can collect data on customer preferences, hours, and menu items.
- Food serving robots are programmed so that they can work on the basis of customer satisfaction.
- With the ability to quickly and accurately fulfill orders, robots have shorter wait time for customers. This leads to customer satisfaction.
- While it is a busy period, the robots can handle it easily.

f) *Disadvantages:*

- The costs of acquiring and implementing food-serving robots can be substantial, posing a barrier for smaller businesses with limited financial resources.
- Robots can experience technical issues or breakdowns, leading to service disruptions and it needs specialized maintenance.
- The adoption of food-serving robots results in displacement for human employees, it raises concerns about unemployment.

- Robots struggle to adapt to situations or handle complex customer interactions that require human intuition and empathy.
- Restaurants relying heavily on food-serving robots may face operational challenges if there are technical failures or disruptions in service.
- The absence of human interaction in dining can lose the human emotions with the customers.
- Training staff to operate and maintain food-serving robots may require significant time and resources.
- Some customers may resist the idea of being served by robots, preferring human interactions.
- Implementing robots in restaurant operations introduces new cybersecurity risks, including the potential for unauthorized access or manipulation of robot functions.
- Questions related to the ethical treatment of robots, potential exploitation of artificial intelligence.

IV. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

[1] The purpose of "The Intelligent Robot for Serving Food" is to explore the implementation and impact of food serving robots in restaurant operations is examined in the study "The Intelligent Robot for Serving Food" by Zainab Khyioon. It explains that the food serving robots are intelligent in their own way. They serve the food and do all the purposes that are needed for the customers. It is published in the year 2022.

[2] The commercial service robots are far from this unreal cinematographic vision. There are well-presented service robots in our daily society, like the cleaner service robot Roomba with an affordable price are examined in the study of "Service Robots in Catering Applications: A Review and Future Challenges" by Juan Miguel García-Haro, Edwin Daniel Oña, Juan Hernandez-Vicen, Santiago Martinez. It investigates that the Robots are applicable to catering services. And it also portrays the future challenges that are implemented with the robotic experience. It is published in the year of 2020

[3] The paper "Waiter Robot – Solution to Restaurant Automation" authored by M Asif. The paper portrays that the Robots are the solutions to restaurant automation. With the implementation of robots in restaurants the customers are well satisfied with their experiences. Compared to human food servers, Robots are really efficient. It was published in the year of 2015.

[4] In "Robotic in Modern-Day Restaurants and its Impact on the Dining Experience" by Amar Dabral, Akash Rawat, Siddhartha Juyal, Satish Joshi the study examines the impact of Robots and the dining experience. In modern days the restaurants are equipped with robotic experience and they all are well equipped serving food.

[5] The paper “Impacts of service robots on service quality” authored by Silvana Trimi. This study explores the service quality provided by robots based on real data in a hotel setting. A sample of 201 guests provided their expected service quality by robots and the actual performance experience after the service. This results in the services provided with the robots with best quality. In the modern days more technological innovations are held upon in the service quality related to robots.

V. METHODS

a) Study Design

This research gives a survey design of Examining the Implementation and Oversight of Food Serving Robots in Restaurant Operations: Insights from Operators in Bangalore. The survey was designed to collect the data on various factors such as implementation on experience, maintenance frequency, impact on speed of service, customer trust, handling customer feedback, preventing disruptions, influence on ambiance and staff training.

b) Participants

The respondents who participated in this study were individuals aged below 18 and above in Bangalore. A survey was used as the main method for gathering data in this study, with the goal of thoroughly examining opinions on Food serving robots in restaurants insights from operators of Bangalore. 101 responses were collected from a diverse group of people to ensure representation across different demographic categories, such as age and gender.

Stratified sampling was used to guarantee proper representation across various age categories. Breaking down the responses by age group, we find that less than 18 year olds provided 30 responses, 18-24 year olds gave 60 responses, 25-35 year olds gave 5 responses, and Above 35 year olds gave 5 responses. Furthermore, the participants were divided based on their gender, with 18 being male and 42 being female.

The survey was carefully crafted to address various important subjects, such as implementation on experience, maintenance frequency, impact on speed of service, customer trust, Handling customer feedback, Preventing disruptions. And Participants show results on Influence on ambiance, Staff Training, Primary reason for oversight, Impact on job roles.

The results of this research are expected to enhance our understanding of the new emerging technologies of the Robotic Restaurants. These findings have the ability to shape upcoming research efforts of Robotic Technologies.

c) Data Collection

Data collection was conducted using an online survey platform called google form, which allows for efficient and convenient data collection. The survey consisted of multiple choice and yes/no questions, covering a range of topics related to Robotic experiences in restaurants.

VI. RESULT

Figure 1

Figure 1 depicts the significant association between implementation experience and the maintenance frequency, as revealed by the ANOVA Test (p value=0.0001). Given that the p-value is less than the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$), we reject the null hypothesis, indicating a clear relationship between these variables. From the analysis we can see that the relation of maintenance frequency and implementation experience are highly related [9][10].

Figure 2

Figure 2 depicts the significant association between impact on speed of service and customer trust, as revealed by the ANOVA Test (p value < 0.0001). With a p-value less than the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$), we reject the null hypothesis, suggesting that

customer trust influences interest in impact on speed of service in public. And the analysis shows that customer trust in public and the impact on speed of service is related[9][11].

Figure 3

Figure 3 depicts the significant association between preventing disruptions and influence on ambiance, which is determined by ANOVA Test (p value=.062). With a p-value less than the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$), we reject the null hypothesis, suggesting that influence on ambiance is related to preventing disruptions. The analysis shows that influence on ambiance related to factors of preventing disruptions[9][10].

Figure 4

Figure 4 depicts the significant association between staff training and primary reason for oversight, which is determined by ANOVA Test (p value < .001). With a p-value less than the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$), we reject the null hypothesis, suggesting that primary reason for oversight influences staff training. The analysis indicates that the primary reason for oversight related to staff training. And it

suggests that the primary reason for oversight related to the staff training factors[12][13].

Figure 5

Figure 5 depicts the significant association between primary reason for oversight and impact on job roles, which is determined by ANOVA Test (p value=.689). With a p-value less than the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$), we reject the null hypothesis, suggesting impact on job roles influences primary reason for oversight. The analysis suggests that impact on job roles perceived impact on primary reason for oversight. This suggests that impact on job roles factors influence the primary reason for oversight [12].

VII . CONCLUSION

The thorough analysis carried out in this study makes it abundantly evident that integrating robots for food serving in restaurants is highly necessary. The results show that a variety of factors, including workload, communication efficacy, career development opportunities, and managerial support, have an impact on performance. The use of robotic solutions is strongly linked to better implementation experiences, such as increased customer trust, service speed, ambiance influence, etc. According to the research, the use of robots in food service positions has the potential to drastically alter how restaurants operate. Organizations must continuously monitor trends in performance satisfaction and methodically assess the efficacy of their intervention measures if they hope to reap these benefits.

This study confirms the significance of investigating the deployment and supervision of food-serving robots by highlighting the revolutionary potential of robotic technologies in the restaurant sector. As a result, the subject of robotic integration in the food service industry is both relevant and vital in today's research and practice, and it is also well-supported by empirical data.

VIII. REFERENCES

- [1] Zainab Khyioon (2022), The Intelligent Robot for Serving Food
- [2] Jee Hye Lee (2021), The Emergence of Service Robots at Restaurants: Integrating Trust, Perceived Risk, and Satisfaction
- [3] Thanh Vo (2019), Development of restaurant serving robot using line following approach
- [4] Christian Vandever, Introduction to Research Statistical Analysis: An Overview of the Basics
- [11] Vera Costa, An Overview of Statistical Data Analysis
- [5] George Argyrous, Statistics for Research With a Guide to SPSS
- [6] Siegmund Brandt, Data Analysis Statistical and Computational Methods for Scientists and Engineers
- [7] Juan Miguel García-Haro, Juan Hernandez-Vicen, Santiago Martinez(2020), Service Robots in Catering Applications: A Review and Future Challenges
- [8] M Asif (2015), Waiter Robot – Solution to Restaurant Automation
- [9] Amar Dabral, Akash Rawat, Siddhartha Juyal, Satish Joshi, Robotic in Modern-Day Restaurants and its Impact on the Dining Experience
- [10] Silvana Trimi, Impacts of service robots on service quality
- [11] Arwa Hamid, Wireless Waiter Robot
- [12] Stanislav H Ivanov, Robots in service experiences: negotiating food tourism in pandemic futures